

Improvement of bioaccumulation of cadmium by *Aspergillus niger* as a function of complex nutrient source

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Abstract : The present study indicated that complex nutrients enhanced bioaccumulation of cadmium by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀. Amongst them, commercial yeast extract showed most prominent effect. Highly significant increment of cadmium accumulation of about 31.2% was observed from a chemically defined medium containing 4 µg/ml of cadmium when the culture medium was supplemented with yeast extract at a concentration of 7.5 mg/ml. Specific composition of a complex nutrient was also found to influence cadmium accumulation. A commercial peptone preparation enriched with tryptophan showed 19.4% increase in bioaccumulation of cadmium, in comparison to peptone without any fortification of tryptophan (9.4% increase). Tryptophan, when supplemented separately in the culture medium, was found to 6.7% increase in cadmium accumulation. The amino acid arginine (8.03% increase) and water-soluble vitamins like ascorbic acid (11.34% increase) and pyridoxine (13.43% increase) were also found to stimulate cadmium uptake in similar cultural conditions.

Keywords : Bioaccumulation, *Aspergillus niger*, cadmium, amino acids, vitamins.

Introduction

The techniques for removal of heavy metals from water bodies are shifting from chemical absorbents to biosorbents, presumably due to the fact that heavy metals are difficult to remove by the natural biogeochemical cycling methods¹ and accumulate in the living bodies through food-chain². For that reason, microbe-based materials became attractive alternatives as they are naturally occurring, and the biomasses from fermentation or other industries can be utilized efficiently in this purpose due to low operational cost³ and minimal formation of residual sludge⁴.

Many microorganisms, including bacteria, fungi, algae and yeasts concentrate heavy metals at different capacities in inactivated or alive conditions^{5,6}. However,

low binding capacities of inactivated/dead biomasses towards specific metals like nickel and failure to remove metals from actual industrial effluents due to the presence of several inorganic and organic ligands limited this approach⁷. In such conditions, metabolically active, preferably metal-resistant microorganisms would ensure better accumulation of metals through a combination of processes like – bioprecipitation, metal adsorption in the cell-surface followed by metabolism driven uptake inside. These are all energy-dependent cellular activities, which need metabolic energy to be replenished by the use of appropriate macro- or micro-nutrients.

Previously in our laboratory, a cadmium resistant strain of *Aspergillus niger* was developed⁸. This resistant strain (viz. *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀) accumulated 91.59% and

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75.76% cadmium from growth medium containing 1 µg/ml and 4 µg/ml cadmium respectively on optimization of various chemical and physical parameters⁹⁻¹¹. The present study was designed to indicate effect of complex nutrients from plant and animal origin on cadmium bioaccumulation, since these are cheap sources of different vitamins, amino acids and minerals acting synergistically on the growth of a microorganism¹². Effect of individual amino acids and vitamins was also observed to adjudicate any synergistic effect on metabolism-driven uptake of cadmium by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀.

Results and discussion

The effect of several complex nutrients, as a metabolic energy sources, on cadmium bioaccumulation by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀ is given in Table 1. Amongst them, yeast extract showed most prominent effect. Significant

Table 1. Effect of complex nutrients on bioaccumulation of cadmium by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀

Results are expressed as mean ($n = 4$) \pm SD

Complex nutrient	Concentration (mg/ml)	Cadmium bioaccumulation (µg/g cell dry weight)
[Control]	-	203.25 \pm 7.44
Yeast extract	1.0	218.55 \pm 4.88 ^b
	2.5	233.79 \pm 6.14 ^a
	5.0	250.66 \pm 6.14 ^a
	7.5	266.75 \pm 5.41 ^a
	10.0	261.10 \pm 7.48 ^a
Peptone (bacteriological) [enriched with tryptophan]	1.0	205.60 \pm 6.34
	2.5	218.27 \pm 4.34 ^a
	5.0	230.50 \pm 4.22 ^a
	7.5	242.72 \pm 4.27 ^a
Peptone M (mycological)	10.0	240.02 \pm 3.85 ^a
	1.0	204.32 \pm 5.18
	2.5	210.36 \pm 6.71
	5.0	215.58 \pm 5.02 ^b
Meat extract	7.5	222.35 \pm 7.42 ^a
	10.0	220.33 \pm 4.62 ^a
	1.0	207.48 \pm 7.11
	2.5	221.73 \pm 3.56 ^b
Corn-steep liquor	5.0	233.94 \pm 3.57 ^a
	7.5	232.40 \pm 3.29 ^a
	10.0	229.78 \pm 2.91 ^b
	1.0	213.49 \pm 2.98 ^b
Paddy-soak liquor	2.5	224.26 \pm 3.38 ^a
	5.0	235.24 \pm 3.48 ^a

Table-1 (contd.)

Paddy-soak liquor	7.5	232.81 \pm 3.33 ^a
	10.0	234.03 \pm 4.88 ^a
	1.0	214.76 \pm 3.04 ^a
	2.5	224.22 \pm 3.12 ^a
	5.0	233.55 \pm 3.32 ^a
	7.5	241.03 \pm 2.52 ^a
	10.0	242.76 \pm 3.94 ^a

^a $p < 0.01$ and ^b $p < 0.05$, compared to control (one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post-hoc test).

increase of cadmium accumulation of about 31.2% in comparison to control [from 203.25 µg/g (control) to 266.75 µg/g cell dry weight] was observed when the culture medium was supplemented with 7.5 mg/ml of yeast extract. It was also observed that amongst the complex nutrients of plant origin used in the present study, only corn-steep liquor and paddy-soak liquor showed significant improvement in the bioaccumulation of cadmium by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀, whereas only one (meat extract) out of five complex nutrients of animal origin, showed significant bioaccumulation. 5 mg/ml of corn-steep liquor and 10 mg/ml paddy-soak liquor in the culture medium improved bioaccumulation by 15.74% and 19.44% respectively, in comparison to the control. In case of 5 mg/ml meat extract, the improvement was 15.10%.

It can easily be perceived that the stimulatory effect of complex nutrients upon cadmium bioaccumulation might be due to the presence of a combination of amino acids, sugars, water-soluble vitamins and trace elements. Influence of a few non-commercial complex nutrients like rice-bran extract and corn-steep liquor on the growth of some filamentous fungi was observed by earlier workers^{13,14}. These nutrients stimulated growth and metabolism of the fungus and the energy-dependent metal uptake mechanism was boosted up.

It was also observed that specific composition of a complex nutrient influenced the cadmium accumulation. The organism showed 19.4% increment of bioaccumulation of cadmium when a commercial peptone preparation enriched with tryptophan was used in the culture medium, in comparison to 9.4% increment in presence of mycological peptone (without tryptophan enrichment) (Table 1). The result indicated that tryptophan or other aromatic amino acids might have some useful role in

bioaccumulation of cadmium. This result was supported when several individual amino acids were supplemented in the culture medium to observe their effect on cadmium bioaccumulation. The results are given in Table 2. It was observed that aromatic amino acids like tryptophan

Table 2. Effect of amino acids on bioaccumulation of cadmium by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀
Results are expressed as mean (n = 4) ±SD

Amino acids	Concentration (mg/ml)	Cadmium bioaccumulation (µg/g cell dry weight)
[Control]	-	203.25 ± 7.44
Glycine	0.75	206.62 ± 3.42
	1.0	209.66 ± 3.05
	2.0	213.02 ± 3.73 ^b
	2.5	212.51 ± 3.32 ^b
Leucine	0.5	205.16 ± 6.55
	0.75	211.20 ± 4.39
	1.0	214.28 ± 2.51 ^b
	2.0	217.81 ± 4.72 ^a
Proline	0.5	203.60 ± 3.65
	0.75	205.92 ± 4.09
	1.0	212.39 ± 3.36
	2.0	213.41 ± 4.09 ^b
Phenylalanine	0.5	202.72 ± 7.68
	0.75	204.29 ± 3.69
	1.0	210.85 ± 4.60
	2.0	216.13 ± 4.24 ^b
Tryptophan	2.5	214.90 ± 4.64 ^b
	0.5	202.51 ± 4.51
	0.75	204.25 ± 3.72
	1.0	212.03 ± 4.60
Cysteine	2.0	216.99 ± 3.08 ^a
	2.5	216.81 ± 3.84 ^a
	0.5	203.12 ± 2.63
	0.75	204.76 ± 4.95
Arginine	1.0	210.97 ± 4.36
	2.0	211.79 ± 3.22
	0.5	202.67 ± 5.80
	0.75	203.61 ± 5.20
Arginine	1.0	209.88 ± 4.84
	2.0	218.40 ± 4.47
	2.5	219.57 ± 3.41

^ap < 0.01 and ^bp < 0.05, compared to control (one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post-hoc test).

(6.71% increment) and phenylalanine (6.34% increment) boosted cadmium accumulation. This might be due to the

participation of aromatic amino acids in coenzyme Q biosynthesis, one of the essential components of the energy-producing reactions in mitochondria. Amongst other amino acids, arginine showed the maximum stimulatory effect (8.03% increment), when supplemented at a concentration of 2.5 mg/ml. Glycine (4.81% increment), leucine (6.18% increment), proline (5.00% increment) and cysteine (4.20% increment) also showed stimulatory effect on cadmium bioaccumulation in comparison to control.

Effects of some water-soluble vitamins on cadmium bioaccumulation by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀ are given in Table 3. Ascorbic acid (11.34% increment), pyridoxine (13.43% increment) and nicotinic acid (8.80% increment)

Table 3. Effect of water soluble vitamins on bioaccumulation of cadmium by *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀
Results are expressed as mean (n = 4) ±SD

Vitamins	Concentration (µg/ml)	Cadmium bioaccumulation (µg/g cell dry weight)
[Control]	-	203.25 ± 7.44
Ascorbic acid	5	206.25 ± 6.34
	10	219.00 ± 2.84 ^a
	15	225.47 ± 4.30 ^a
	20	226.34 ± 4.94 ^a
Pyridoxine	5	210.32 ± 4.59
	10	218.86 ± 5.59 ^a
	15	229.20 ± 5.05 ^a
	20	230.54 ± 5.03 ^a
Nicotinic acid	5	200.25 ± 3.77
	10	206.13 ± 4.51
	15	219.69 ± 4.90 ^a
	20	221.13 ± 4.03 ^a

^ap < 0.01 and ^bp < 0.05, compared to control (one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post-hoc test).

showed significant stimulatory effect. This was in accordance with the fact that yeast extract, which generally contains a number of water-soluble vitamins, showed prominent stimulatory effect in the present study (Table 1). However, stimulatory effect of individual vitamins or amino acids on cadmium accumulation did not exceed the stimulatory effect of the complex nutrients, since synergistic effect of all these biomolecules would be essential for their proper functioning. Complex nutrients might provide such synergism. This shows promising possibilities of cadmium removal from aqueous systems with the use of commercially available complex

nutrients as composite sources of amino acids, vitamins and other useful macromolecules for the fungus, which would definitely take care of the economical aspects when applied in large-scale industrial processes.

Experimental

All the chemicals, except the complex nutrients, were purchased from Merck or Loba (AR grade). Complex nutrients of best qualities were purchased from either CDH or Oxoid-Merck. Preparation of non-commercial complex nutrients is described below. All the culture media preparation was done using double-distilled water.

Preparation of rice-bran and wheat-bran liquor : 20 g of each liquors were taken in 200 ml of warm distilled water separately. The suspensions were kept at 55 °C for 18 h. The extracts were filtered separately through cotton and evaporated to dryness under vacuum to recover the solid materials.

Preparation of corn-steep liquor : 100 g of thoroughly washed maize was taken in 250 ml of distilled water containing 0.52% potassium meta-bisulfite. The suspension was kept at 55 °C for 48 h. The extract was filtered through cotton and evaporated to dryness under vacuum to recover the solid material.

Preparation of paddy-soak liquor : 200 g thoroughly washed paddy was taken in 200 ml of distilled water and allowed to soak water for 2 h at 55 °C till the grain swelled completely. The soaked water was filtered through cotton and evaporated to dryness under vacuum to recover the solid material.

A cadmium resistant strain of *Aspergillus niger* (viz. *Aspergillus niger* AB₁₀) was developed and maintained as described previously⁸. Composition of the synthetic culture media for metal uptake experiments as well as other culture conditions was also described⁸. Complex nutrients were supplemented in the culture media at concentrations of 1.0, 2.5, 5.0, 7.5 and 10.0 mg/ml. Amino acids were supplemented at concentrations of 0.5, 0.75, 1 and 2 mg/ml; and the vitamins were supplemented at concentrations of 5, 10, 15 and 20 µg/ml. The cell mass were separated by filtration, washed thoroughly with

double distilled water, digested with 6 (N) HNO₃, and the cadmium content was analyzed by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer after optimum period of incubation⁸. The amount of cadmium accumulated by the microorganism was calculated by calculating the biomass metal loading, according to a formula described elsewhere¹⁵.

All the data, in the present study, were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post-hoc test for multiple comparisons of the treatment means using 'Prism 4.0' software (GraphPad Inc., USA). A *p*-value of 0.01 or less was taken as criteria for a statistically significant difference.

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